

Co-liberation of Hydrogen and Oxygen at the Anode and Cathode during Electrolysis

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Hydrogen prepared by electrolysis usually contains a small percentage of oxygen and this is generally attributed to diffusion from the anode¹. The present author however reported² that during electrolysis accompanied by glow (to be called glow electrolysis or galvano-luminescence) the cathode gas contains a large percentage of oxygen which is often as high as twenty per cent and in some cases much higher. Such observations have led the author to investigate how far such co-liberation of hydrogen and oxygen at the same electrode (to be called, simply, co-liberation) takes place in ordinary electrolysis. It is now found that such co-liberation can be easily brought about under suitable conditions and the present note is a preliminary report of the same.

RESULTS

We have found that co-liberation is a universal phenomenon, particularly at low concentration, and low current with almost all electrolytes which liberate hydrogen and oxygen. The phenomenon can be strikingly observed during electrolysis of water and the present paper reports our results with water. Our experimental set-up for this work

Fig. 1 Electrolysis cell with bright platinum electrodes (1 cm. x 1 cm.)

is shown in Fig. 1. Current was passed through a constant current apparatus. Hydrogen and oxygen were analysed by direct slow combustion of the gas itself (often the cathode gas as well as the anode gas exploded at this step) followed by the usual method of analysis of hydrogen-oxygen mixture on the remaining gas. The explosions leave no doubt that a mixture forms at both the electrodes. A set of typical results is shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Electrolyte	Run No.	Voltage	Current mA	Time hrs	Cathode Gas*				Anode Gas*			
					V_{FC} cc	V_C cc	%H ₂	%O ₂	V_{FA} cc	V_A cc	%O ₂	%H ₂
Conductivity	1	560 to	0.3	211	29.6	7.85	77.29	22.71	14.8	3.85	39.2	60.8
Water	2	600 Volts	0.35	189hr 50'	31.0	10.50	72.4	27.6	15.5	1.60	41.6	58.4
	3		0.4	142hr 15'	26.2	8.65	71.3	28.7	13.1	1.70	41.2	58.8
	4		0.42	96	18.8	6.90	70.4	29.6	9.4	1.65	39.4	60.6

* V_{FC} = Volume of hydrogen to be liberated at cathode according to Faraday's law at the experimental temperature (corrected for aqueous tension);

V_C = Volume of hydrogen and oxygen actually liberated at cathode;

V_{FA} & V_A have similar significance with respect to anode;

The results in Table I show the following features (ignoring the data of the first run which is usually quite different).

(1) The volume of gas liberated at the cathode far exceeds that liberated at the anode. Under our experimental condition the former is about four to six times that of the latter.

(2) The volume of gas liberated at each electrode falls far short of that prescribed by Faraday's law (V_F). At the cathode the observed volume (V_C) is about one-third of the theoretical (V_{FC}), whereas at the anode, the observed volume (V_A) is one-sixth to one-ninth of the theoretical (V_{FA}). Total volume (V) liberated is one-third to one-fourth of the theoretical expected volume (V_F). This confirms our previous observation³ that at low current and low concentration there is strong negative deviation from Faraday's law indicating its possible non-validity.

(3) The most unexpected feature of the results shown in Table I is that the cathode gas contains a large percentage of oxygen and the anode gas contains more than fifty per cent hydrogen. The total oxygen however is somewhat less than the stoichiometric proportion probably due to hydrogen peroxide formation.

Inter-electrode diffusion can not account for the above observations for the following reasons. The electrodes are too far, the gas liberation is non-turbulent, and control experiments with 0.5N K₂SO₄ (an ideal coulometric solution⁴) in series shows a far better conformity with Faraday's law and much smaller extent of co-liberation. It is thus established beyond

reasonable doubt that water shows pronounced departure from Faraday's law in electrolysis. As a matter of fact, such non-Faradaic behaviour, though different from case to case, is shown by many other electrolytes, for example, sodium hydroxide, sodium sulphate, sulphuric acid, etc., provided the solutions are sufficiently dilute and the current is kept low. We shall report our results with solutions in later publications.

DISCUSSION

The Faraday-Hittorf mechanism is evidently unable to take care of the above observations. We believe that current is conducted through solution by three concurrent mechanisms: (1) by the classical Faraday-Hittorf ionic transport mechanism; (2) by electronic conduction as in many crystals where both (1) and (2) operate side by side; and (3) by a mechanism which operates in glow electrolysis and which possibly is a kind of electric discharge probably through a thin layer of gas causing electron investment and abstraction near the electrodes bringing about chemical reactions (decomposition of water) not envisaged by the classical mechanism. For brevity, we shall call these three mechanisms of current conduction as follows: (1) Classical mechanism or ionic conduction, (2) Electronic conduction and (3) Discharge mechanism respectively. If ions are in plenty (i.e. at higher concentration of the electrolyte) mechanism (1) takes precedence over the non-Faradaic mechanisms (2) and (3), whereas at higher voltage and paucity of ions the current tends to prefer the non-Faradaic reaction paths. It is surprising that the universally accepted Faraday's law should have so much deficiency gone undetected over such a long time.

The necessity of postulating three concurrent mechanisms is as follows. The classical mechanism needs no comment. The electronic mechanism is needed to explain the fact that in such electrolysis the chemical decomposition is very much less than that prescribed by Faraday's law. The third mechanism i.e. the discharge mechanism is simply an extrapolation of the observations made during glow electrolysis². Since glow electrolysis is accompanied by considerable co-liberation, it is assumed that the same mechanism (without specifying any details as to the actual steps) is also concurrently operative. This accounts for the co-liberation, and the higher decomposition at the cathode is easily attributable to electronic bombardment.

It should be pointed out that water as an electrolyte is an extreme case of paucity of ionic carriers. As a result, non-Faradaic mechanisms operate to a large extent resulting in a pronounced negative deviation from Faraday's law and the large co-liberation of hydrogen and oxygen in both the electrodes. However, such non-Faradaic mechanisms may operate more or less even in ordinary electrolysis. Therefore, the low current efficiency in many electrolysis need not necessarily be attributed to side reactions but may at least in part be caused by electronic conduction; and the occurrence of oxygen in electrolytic hydrogen (or for that matter, hydrogen in electrolytic oxygen) may be due to some kind of concurrent electronic mechanism.

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R E F E R E N C E S

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